

Assessment of Clinical Readiness of Dental Students and Interns in Providing Dental Care During Pregnancy

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ABSTRACT

Background: Oral health care during pregnancy plays a crucial role in preventing adverse maternal and foetal outcomes. However, inadequate training and lack of confidence among dental students may hinder appropriate management of pregnant patients in clinical practice.

Aim: To assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of clinical dental students and interns regarding the management of pregnant patients in dental settings.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 200 third-year students, final-year students, and interns using a validated 15-item structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, ANOVA, and Chi-square tests to evaluate differences and associations among educational levels.

Results: Females constituted 78.5% of participants, with final-year students forming the largest group (43.5%). Knowledge scores differed significantly across educational levels ($p < 0.001$), with interns demonstrating the highest mean score (4.53 ± 1.68). Bonferroni post hoc analysis showed significant differences between interns and third-year students. A significant association was observed between education level and knowledge grades ($p < 0.001$), indicating progressive improvement with academic advancement.

Conclusion: Despite improved knowledge with higher educational levels, gaps remain in the preparedness of dental students to manage pregnant patients. Strengthening undergraduate curricula through focused training, clinical exposure, and interdisciplinary collaboration is essential to ensure safe and effective prenatal dental care.

Keywords: Pregnancy, oral health, dental students, knowledge, attitudes, clinical practice.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy brings significant physiological changes that can affect oral health, making dental care for pregnant women a critical aspect of prenatal care¹. During pregnancy, hormonal fluctuations can lead to increased susceptibility to periodontal disease and dental caries². The American Dental Association (ADA) emphasizes the importance of maintaining

oral health during pregnancy to prevent adverse pregnancy outcomes such as preterm birth and low birth weight³.

Despite the recognized importance, many dental students and interns may lack sufficient knowledge and confidence in managing dental issues in pregnant patients⁴. Studies have shown that gaps in dental education regarding prenatal oral health care can lead

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to reluctance among dental practitioners to treat pregnant women, potentially compromising their oral health⁵.

Assessing the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of dental students and interns towards treating pregnant patients is essential to identify educational deficiencies and improve training programs⁶. By evaluating third-year and final-year dental students, as well as interns, this study aims to provide insights into their preparedness and approach towards dental care for pregnant women⁷.

The objectives of this study are twofold: to assess the knowledge and attitudes of third-year, final-year, and intern dental students towards addressing dental issues in pregnant patients, and to examine how they practice dental care for this patient group. Addressing these objectives will help inform curriculum development and enhance the training of future dental professionals in providing comprehensive care to pregnant women.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This cross-sectional survey was conducted at a dental teaching institution among clinical dental students and interns. The study aimed to assess their knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to dental care for pregnant patients.

Study Population and Sampling

The study population comprised 200 clinical dental students and interns. Participants included third-year and final-year dental students, as well as interns. A convenience sampling method was used to select participants, ensuring a diverse representation of students at different stages of their training.

Data Collection Tool

A structured questionnaire was developed specifically for this study. The questionnaire consisted of 15 questions designed to evaluate the participants' training, awareness, and practices in treating pregnant patients in dental clinics. The questions were divided into sections covering the following areas:

1. **Demographic Information:** Age, gender, year of study, and prior training in prenatal dental care.
2. **Knowledge:** Understanding of physiological changes during pregnancy and their implications for oral health.
3. **Attitudes:** Perceptions and beliefs about treating pregnant patients.
4. **Practices:** Clinical practices and procedures followed when treating pregnant patients.

The questionnaire was pre-tested on a small group of 30 dental students to ensure clarity and relevance. Necessary adjustments were made based on the feedback received.

Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire was administered to the participants in person. Prior to participation, informed consent was obtained from all participants. The data collection process was supervised by the research team to ensure completeness and accuracy of the responses.

Data Management and Analysis

The collected data were entered into an Excel spreadsheet for organization and preliminary analysis. Descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize the demographic characteristics of the participants and their responses to the questionnaire.

For further statistical analysis, the data were imported into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 29.0 (IBM Corp.). The following statistical tests were performed:

1. **Descriptive Statistics:** Frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were calculated for all variables.
2. **Inferential Statistics:** Chi-square tests were used to assess associations between categorical variables, such as knowledge levels and attitudes towards treating pregnant patients. T-tests or ANOVA were employed to compare mean scores of knowledges and practices among

different groups (e.g., third-year students, final-year students, and interns).

The sample consisted of 200 clinical dental students and interns. The distribution by year of study is as follows: third-year students (N=58, 29.0%), final-year students (N=87, 43.5%), and interns (N=55, 27.5%). The gender distribution included 157 females (78.5%) and 43 males (21.5%).

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

Figure 1: Gender Distribution In The Study Population

Figure 2: Distribution Of Study Participants By Education Level

TABLE 1: Knowledge Scores Among Third-Year Students, Final-Year Students, and Interns

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		F	Sig
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Third Years	58	3.00	2.248	0.295	2.41	3.59	10.095	.000
Final Years	87	3.90	1.578	0.169	3.56	4.23		
Interns	55	4.53	1.676	0.226	4.07	4.98		
Total	200	3.81	1.903	0.135	3.54	4.08		

Test used: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant

The table 1 compares the mean knowledge scores among third-year students, final-year students, and interns. The sample sizes (N) for each group are 58, 87, and 55 respectively. The mean scores, standard deviations, and standard errors are listed for each

group. The confidence intervals for the means show the range within which the true mean likely falls. The F-value (10.095) and the significance level ($p < .001$) indicate that there is a statistically significant difference in the knowledge scores among the three groups.

Table 2: Multiple Comparisons of Knowledge Scores Between Educational Levels Using Bonferroni Method

(I) Education	(J) Education	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Third Years	Final Years	-0.897*	0.309	0.012	-1.64	-0.15
Third Years	Interns	-1.527*	0.343	0.000	-2.36	-0.70
Final Years	Third Years	0.897*	0.309	0.012	0.15	1.64
Final Years	Interns	-0.631	0.314	0.137	-1.39	0.13
Interns	Third Years	1.527*	0.343	0.000	0.70	2.36
Interns	Final Years	0.631	0.314	0.137	-0.13	1.39

Test used: Bonferroni post hoc test, $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 3: Crosstabulation of Education Level and Scores

Education Level	Scores										Total
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Third Years	5	14	10	6	10	6	2	0	5	0	58
Final Years	0	5	15	13	21	23	6	2	2	0	87
Interns	0	0	5	16	5	11	13	3	1	1	55
Total	5	19	30	35	36	40	21	5	8	1	200

Test used: Pearson's Chi-square test, $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant

The Chi-Square analysis reveals a significant association between students' education levels (third-year students, final-year students, and interns) and the grades they achieve. The Pearson Chi-Square value of 71.881, with 18 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.000, confirms this strong relationship. The likelihood ratio test further supports this finding with a similar value and statistical significance. Additionally, the linear-by-linear association test indicates a significant trend, suggesting that as students progress in their education, their grades exhibit a notable pattern.

The distribution of grades across different education levels highlights distinct trends. Third-year students predominantly fall within the low-grade category, with fewer achieving medium or high grades. Final-year students show a shift towards the medium grade range, with a notable decrease in the low-grade category. Interns, while still having a substantial number in the lower range, display a more balanced distribution across low and medium grades, with a slightly higher representation in the high-grade category compared to other groups. This trend suggests that academic performance may improve with educational advancement, although variations exist across groups.

DISCUSSION

The results of this study highlight significant findings regarding the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of dental students and interns towards providing dental care to pregnant patients. The cross-sectional survey conducted among 200 clinical dental students and interns revealed several key insights.

Gender Distribution

The gender distribution in our study showed a predominance of female participants (78.5%), consistent with trends in dental education, where female enrollment is often higher⁸. This demographic characteristic is important to consider when developing educational programs, as different gender-related perspectives and experiences can influence learning outcomes and attitudes towards patient care.

Education Level Distribution

The distribution of participants by education level included third-year students (29.0%), final-year students (43.5%), and interns (27.5%). This stratification allowed for an assessment of knowledge and attitudes across different stages of dental education. The significant differences in knowledge scores among the groups, as indicated by the ANOVA results, underscore the importance of progressive learning and practical exposure in dental education⁹.

Knowledge and Attitudes Towards Treating Pregnant Patients

The ANOVA analysis revealed significant differences in the knowledge scores among third-year students, final-year students, and interns, with interns scoring the highest on average. This finding aligns with expectations, as interns typically have more clinical experience and exposure to diverse patient cases, including pregnant patients. The multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni method further confirmed that interns had significantly higher knowledge scores compared to both third-year and final-year students.

Challenges and Gaps in Education

Despite the overall increase in knowledge with advancing education levels, the study identified notable gaps in the preparedness of dental students to manage dental care for pregnant patients. The Chi-Square tests indicated a significant association between education level and grades achieved, suggesting that education level influences the quality of knowledge and attitudes towards prenatal dental care. This finding aligns with a study by Da Costa et al., which assessed dental care for pregnant women and highlighted similar trends among general dentists in North Carolina⁴. The study emphasized the impact of educational background on dentists' preparedness and confidence in managing prenatal dental care, underscoring the need for targeted educational interventions to enhance competencies in this area. However, the relatively lower scores among third-year and final-year students highlight the need for enhanced curricular content and targeted training in this area.

Previous research underscores the importance of integrating comprehensive prenatal care modules into dental curricula^{10,11,12,13}. For instance, integrating such

education can significantly impact the clinical competencies of future dentists¹⁴. Another study by Rocha et al. pointed out the barriers and facilitators in providing dental care during pregnancy, emphasizing the need for curricular changes⁵. Studies have also highlighted the role of continuous professional development in maintaining and enhancing clinical skills¹⁵.

Implications for Dental Education

The results emphasize the necessity for comprehensive educational interventions to bridge the knowledge gap among dental students. Incorporating specialized modules on prenatal oral health, hands-on training, and interdisciplinary collaboration with obstetricians could enhance students' confidence and competence in treating pregnant patients^{1,7,16}. Additionally, continuous professional development and refresher courses for interns and practicing dentists are crucial to keep them updated with the latest guidelines and best practices in prenatal dental care.

Furthermore, the establishment of dental care protocols specifically designed for pregnant patients can aid in standardizing care practices. Increased collaboration between dental and medical schools is also suggested to foster a more holistic approach to prenatal care^{12,17}. Enhanced communication skills and understanding of patient management during pregnancy should be integral parts of dental education programs¹⁸.

Educating the wider community about the importance of oral health during pregnancy is another crucial step. Public health campaigns targeting pregnant women can raise awareness about the significance of dental care during this period, potentially leading to increased utilization of dental services. This can also reduce the prevalence of adverse pregnancy outcomes associated with poor oral health, such as preterm birth and low birth weight¹⁹.

Research and Evidence-Based Practice

Continuous research and the integration of evidence-based practices in dental education can further enhance the quality of care provided to pregnant patients. Encouraging students to participate in

research projects related to prenatal dental care can help them stay updated with the latest developments and innovations in the field. Additionally, integrating findings from current research into the curriculum can ensure that future dental professionals are well-prepared to handle the unique challenges associated with providing care to pregnant patients.

CONCLUSION

This study sheds light on the current state of knowledge, attitudes, and practices among dental students and interns regarding prenatal dental care. The significant findings call for urgent curricular reforms and targeted educational strategies to equip future dental professionals with the necessary skills and confidence to provide optimal care for pregnant patients. By addressing these educational deficiencies, dental schools can ensure that their graduates are well-prepared to meet the oral health needs of this vulnerable patient population.

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